

INQUIRY REPORT · 13 APRIL 2026

Youth Connect.

Fundão (PT) · Córdoba (ES) · Riga (LV)

fundão
365 dias à descoberta

Co-funded by
the European Union

COORDINATOR

Municipality of Fundão (PT)

PARTNERS

Estrellas del Sur (ES)

CEIR (LV)

PROGRAMME

Erasmus+ KA210-YOU

Small-scale Partnership in
Youth

02 · CONTENTS

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What young migrants told us about digital inclusion in three European cities, alongside what youth workers see in their daily work. The closing section sets out where the project goes from here.

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03

About the YouthConnect Project.

An Erasmus+ project working with young migrants and refugees in Latvia, Portugal and Spain, around three things: getting online, finding a way into work, and feeling part of the place they now live in.

03.1 · RELEVANCE

Relevance of the project.

YouthConnect is an Erasmus+ **Small-scale partnership in youth (KA210-YOU)** aimed at strengthening **digital inclusion, employability pathways and community participation** for **young migrants and refugees**. For achieving this, the project focuses on training youth workers who support municipalities, youth organisations and a research centre in the partner countries - Latvia, Portugal and Spain.

The YouthConnect project aligns with Erasmus+ priorities on **digital transformation**. The project also fits with youth priorities on **recognising and improving youth work** and **strengthening employability**.

YouthConnect focuses on the partner organizations' capacity building in youth work and training of **everyday digital skills** to young people with disadvantaged backgrounds to strengthen their motivation, **inclusion and connectedness to real-life needs in host countries**.

Across **Fundão (Portugal), Córdoba (Spain) and Riga (Latvia)**, YouthConnect is highly relevant to practical realities of the modern societies in these countries. Today digital tools, having become indispensable in learning, work, housing, health, and public services, ensure equitable access for social and economic participation. However, uneven digital access or confidence can create barriers to participation and inclusion, especially impacting young people in a new host country.

03.2 Target groups

GROUP A

Young Migrants & Refugees

Primarily **16-25** in host countries, especially those who face barriers to access to digital opportunities for their participation and social inclusion.

GROUP B

Youth Workers & Professionals

Primarily **18-35** (YW / IWMR staff), who incorporate digital methods and tools into learning in non-formal education (NFE) to enhance young migrants' social and professional inclusion in host countries.

3 KEY ACTIVITIES

- **Inquiry of needs:** an inquiry of needs of young migrants and refugees in host countries is prepared by reaching around 150 young migrants and 60 youth workers across the three participating countries.
- **Training:** training of 15 youth workers of the partner organizations is organized.
- **Digital skills development:** the development of digital skills is provided to around 80 young migrants.

03.3 · THE PARTNERSHIP

The partnership.

YouthConnect is implemented by the partners from the European Union's countries. The partner demonstrated the appropriate mix of necessary profiles, skills and expertise in youth work and training. Each partner organization cooperates with **institutions working with migrants and refugees (IWMRs)** and local stakeholders in their countries to ensure the project is grassrooted into local reality of migration and integration services as well as youth-support organisations.

COORDINATOR · PORTUGAL**Municipality of Fundão**

Coordinating role, bringing extensive experience in municipal youth work and local integration.

PARTNER · SPAIN**Estrellas del Sur**

Córdoba. Contributing expertise in youth work practice and training.

PARTNER · LATVIA**Centre for Education & Innovation Research (CEIR)**

Riga. Providing competent support in research initiatives and project evaluation.

TOGETHER**A grassrooted consortium**

Each partner cooperates with local IWMRs and stakeholders to ensure the project is grassrooted into local reality of migration and integration services.

03.4 · WORK PROGRAMME

Work programme.

The YouthConnect project was implemented in a sequential logic and structure: each phase provides the foundation for the next phase. The project started with a structured inquiry using two survey questionnaire forms, one for young migrants and one for youth workers and IWMR professionals.

01 Structured inquiry

The survey questionnaire helped map the daily lives and real challenges of young migrants in host countries: how they access the digital environment, how confident they feel using digital tools, and what learning opportunities they prioritise.

02 Digital NFE Tools & Resources

Inquiry findings informed the design and development of practical and reusable learning activities for immediate use by youth workers. The partnership utilized a prototyping approach: initial drafts tested, peer-reviewed and refined.

03 Training Course (Córdoba)

The course equipped 15 youth workers, five per partner country, with relevant digital competences and non-formal education methods to be used in their daily work with young migrants.

04 Local Workshops

Trained youth workers offered in total 15 sessions (five per partner country) of Digital Workshops on email use, office tools, online services, Europass and collaboration platforms. Also, nine sessions (three per partner country) of Digital Art Storytelling Workshops were provided.

05 YouthConnect Day

Each partner country hosted an event bringing together local youth, young migrants, youth workers, local decision-makers and stakeholders interested in the use of non-formal education methods and activities.

03.5 · OUTPUTS

Project outputs.

YouthConnect produces several tangible outputs and practical resources. All the project deliverables, including inquiry report, educational resources and documented activities, will be provided open access on the **YouthConnect Platform**. An open licence under a Creative Commons Attribution framework is ensured for project results. The YouthConnect Platform will be maintained for at least 3 years after the project ends.

01**Inquiry Report**

Available in EN, PT, ES, LV

02**Digital NFE Tools**

Reusable activities for youth work

03**Training Course**

Piloted by all partners

04

Structured methods

05**Digital Art Storytelling**

Creative inclusion methods

06**YouthConnect Day**

Dissemination materials

OPEN ACCESS

All deliverables published on the YouthConnect Platform under **Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike**. Maintained for at least 3 years after the project ends.

04

Introduction to the Inquiry.

Two surveys, three cities, 223 voices. A practical tool to bridge the needs of young migrants and youth workers with inclusive digital non-formal education.

04.1 · PURPOSE

Purpose of the inquiry.

The inquiry started by going to the people who already work on young migrants' digital inclusion day to day: municipalities, NGOs, youth centres and integration services, among others. Out of all of them, two groups in particular have a clear view of what young migrants actually need in order to settle in.

GROUP A

Young Migrants (YM)

The young migrants themselves, dealing with everyday life, study and work in a country that is still new to them.

GROUP B

Youth Workers / IWMR professionals

The youth workers who sit across from them and try to make inclusion happen in practice.

INQUIRY SECTIONS

INQUIRY SECTION	A SHORT DESCRIPTION
Priority setting	Skills and topics with the strongest need and motivation
Barriers	Devices, data, costs, language, mentoring
Support for learning	Formats, guidance, safe environments, peer support
Trainers' needs	Methods, templates, tool stacks, safeguarding in delivering digital non-formal education (NFE) confidently and sustainably

“

The YouthConnect Inquiry is meant as a working tool, not a finished study: it tries to line up what both groups say they need with the kind of digital non-formal education we can actually put on the table.

04.2 · RESPONDENTS

Respondents.

The Inquiry is structured into **two complementary forms** with the focus on the needs of each target group. The analysis of two perspectives, namely young migrants and youth workers, is beneficial for all the interested in digital non-formal education: if their perspectives coincide, the digital non-formal education is based on both groups' informed choices and proceeds in a natural manner; if the perspectives differ, targeted novel educational measures are implemented to increase participants' motivation and engagement.

223

Total valid responses

153

Young Migrants

70

Youth Workers / IWMR
professionals

RESPONSES PER COUNTRY

LOCATION	TOTAL RESPONSES	% OF TOTAL
Riga (Latvia)	72	32.3%
Córdoba (Spain)	77	34.5%
Fundão (Portugal)	74	33.2%
Total	223	100%

NOTE ON CITY DATA

It is worth noting that the survey does not include a "city name" question because all responses were collected locally from young migrants and professionals living/working in Fundão (Portugal), Córdoba (Spain), and Riga (Latvia). All 223 responses are valid. Some cells in the spreadsheet may appear blank, resulting from the inquiry structure (multiple language versions of the same questions and questions adapted for each target group).

05

Respondents' Profiles.

Who they are, where they're from, what they do, the people behind the data.

05.1 · YOUNG MIGRANTS

Young Migrants - age and profile.

Most young migrant respondents are in **early adulthood**, a life stage where education, first jobs, and building independence often overlap. The collected data allow finding that the majority of the respondents may still be navigating transitions to a higher educational level and youth protection systems, depending on the local context.

AGE GROUPS

GENDER

The inquiry discloses a balanced distribution of the respondents' gender. This helps mapping the views from the perspectives of both genders that can be useful for the organization of inclusive digital non-formal education.

49.7%

Male · n=76

47.1%

Female · n=72

TIME SPENT IN THE HOST COUNTRY

The time period, spent by the respondents in a host country, differs significantly. This mix implies different starting points: newcomers may need more support with **language and services navigation**, while those more settled may be ready to focus more strongly on **employment pathways and longer-term planning**.

— 05.2 · YM STATUS

Educational and occupational status.

Youth migrants' responses provide evidence that the majority of them is in the stage of upper secondary/VET pathways (68.6%, n=105). This finding suggests that young migrants are simultaneously involved in education and search for employment. Therefore, the inquiry reveals that practical youth work should focus on digital learning to connect young migrants' education and employability.

EDUCATIONAL AND OCCUPATIONAL STATUS

— KEY FINDING

Overall, young migrants are **highly motivated to use digital tools** to increase their social inclusion in host countries.

05.3 · YOUTH WORKERS

Youth workers - profile.

Youth workers are the key persons who serve young migrant. Therefore, their role in young migrants' social inclusion is crucial. The collected data shows that the majority of the respondents are young people themselves. Gender representation of the respondents leans female (54.3%, n=38), which reflects a common situation in youth and social services. Most of the respondents, who are youth workers, have **higher education** (77.1%, n=54). This suggests that the respondents have an appropriate qualification to organize qualitative, inclusive and accessible non-formal education and methods.

AGE GROUPS

54.3%

Female representation (n=38)

77.1%

Higher education qualification (n=54)

76.9%

0-10 years working experience

MIX OF EXPERIENCE

The collected data informs that levels of working experience of youth workers in youth support vary. This mix of both experienced and beginners' youth workers is valuable as it means non-formal education can build a quality and inclusion training through **confidence, structure and session design** to be provided by novel youth workers, and **advanced methods, coordination and scaling** by more experienced youth workers.

06

Young Migrants.

Highly motivated. Often blocked by structural conditions. Here's what their voices reveal.

06.1 · DIGITAL ACCESS

Digital access and connectivity.

8 of 10 young migrants **use the internet every day**. This shows that the majority of the respondents have daily contact with the online environment. The inquiry's results show that the majority of the respondents in the cities of Fundão (Portugal), Córdoba (Spain) and Riga (Latvia) daily use the internet.

78.4%

Daily internet access

52.3%

Own a laptop / computer

35.9%

Blocked by access/tech problems

DAILY USE OF THE INTERNET IN THE CITIES OF THE PARTNER COUNTRIES

LOCATION	YM (N)	DAILY INTERNET (%)
Fundão (Portugal)	33	76.7%
Córdoba (Spain)	34	82.9%
Riga (Latvia)	38	74.5%

— POSSESSION OF OWN LAPTOP OR COMPUTER

The inquiry's results show that nearly half of the respondents do not have their own laptop or computer. The results help finding that the lack of own laptops or computers affect the respondents' use of online forms like Europass CVs, school platforms, public service and other important platforms. The assumption here is that a significant number of the respondents use their phones for handle their online daily routines.

06.1 · ACCESS PROBLEMS

Connection problems.

The responses demonstrate that more than one third of the respondents experienced problems with the online connection. One fifth of them sometimes had the connection problems. The finding for the YouthConnect project is that unreliable infrastructure continues to impede full participation of young migrants in digital non-formal education. The inconsistent accessibility to the digital environment remains a persistent obstacle for a significant number of the respondents, deepening the digital divide in local communities.

ONLINE CONNECTION PROBLEMS IN THE CITIES OF THE PARTNER COUNTRIES

LOCATION	YM (N)	ANY ACCESS/TECH PROBLEM (%)*
Fundão (Portugal)	27	62.8%
Córdoba (Spain)	21	51.2%
Riga (Latvia)	31	60.8%

* "Any access/tech problem" = Yes or Sometimes.

MEANS OF ONLINE CONNECTION

Home internet		49.0%
Mobile data		42.5%

“

"No tengo Internet en casa, por lo tanto no puedo hacer muchas cosas en casa."

“

"Na parte do carregamento e da conectividade."

— IMPLICATION

Combining these inquiry's results, only each 4 of 10 respondents have a permanent connection to the internet. The other 6 of 10 respondents rely on public Wi-Fi or shared spaces, making their access to digital non-formal education and social services unstable. Therefore, the quality and stability of that connection may vary significantly, impacting the quality of non-formal education methods.

06.2 · DIGITAL SKILLS

Digital skills and confidence.

According to the inquiry results, young migrants report a mixed confidence as 2 of 10 respondents have difficulties with Office tools (Word, Excel, PowerPoint) and online forms. This shows each 2nd of 10 respondents needs support in tasks with the use of **office tools** and **filling online forms**. These results support the finding that non-formal education content should be inclusive, attractive, qualitative to the young people with different levels of competence. Non-formal education is not a "one-size-fits-all" model. Better support to every learner has to be provided.

LOW CONFIDENCE AREAS (RATED 1-2)

— PRIVACY AND PERSONAL INFORMATION ONLINE

Over one third of the respondents rated their privacy skills low. The respondents indicated that they feel unsure about **privacy and personal information online**.

— ONLINE MEETINGS

About 3 in 10 respondents rated their joining and using online meetings (Zoom/Teams/Meet) as low. Difficulties with online meetings, video calls and video conferencing can lead them to their non-participation in non-formal education, medical appointments, job interviews, and vital social services. This can bring them negative consequences in their socio-economic inclusion.

“

"Tratar de vírus e publicidade indesejada."

06.3 · LEARNING NEEDS

Learning needs.

The inquiry's results reveal that each 6 of 10 respondents needs support in **job search and CV tools**. More than half of the respondents wish to develop their **basic computer and internet skills**. The finding is that even if someone is online daily, they may still not feel confident with the skills needed for school, work and services. Each 4th of 10 respondents is interested to learn about **AI tools, creative tools for design and storytelling, and online communication/collaboration tools**.

NEEDS OF THE RESPONDENTS IN DIGITAL NON-FORMAL EDUCATION

“

"AI tools to create CVs and help with translation and writing."

SHIFT IN NEEDS

The data suggests that there is a shift from basic navigation to higher-level engagement. Young people need **more than digital survival functions**. They also wish digital tools that help shape their lives. Organization of training of young people digital skills in non-formal education should include job-related learning that can be a great way to teach basics (files, email, forms) with a clear purpose, and creative tools that can boost confidence and participation if done safely and respectfully.

06.4 · BARRIERS

Barriers.

Financial barriers related to purchase and maintenance of devices, data, or tools, are the leading obstacle for each 4 of the 10 respondents. Each 4th of 10 respondents does not know **where to learn**. Therefore, existing learning opportunities are not visible and accessible. Another critical barrier for each 3rd of 10 respondents is the need in **support from a mentor or helper**. If young people are guided through the confusing parts of the learning process, their results are better. Lack of device, time constraints, and language barrier are stressed by more than 2 of 10 respondents. Anxiety/low confidence is experienced by 2 of 10 respondents.

BARRIERS THE RESPONDENTS FACE IN DIGITAL NON-FORMAL EDUCATION

06.5 · LEARNING FORMATS

Preferred learning formats.

The most preferred learning format about 4 of 10 respondents is **in-person workshops**. **Mixed learning**, the combination of in-person and online, is supported by 2 of 10 respondents. Fully online sessions are less preferred by the respondents as around 2 of 10 respondents supported this type of learning. This suggests that face-to-face is acknowledged by young migrants for building trust, confidence, and troubleshooting. Overall, young migrants most often prefer learning that provide them with **human communication and support**.

RESPONDENTS' PREFERRED LEARNING FORMATS

RESPONDENTS' PREFERRED SUPPORTERS

SUPPORT SOURCE	N	%
Friends / family	55	35.9%
Youth worker / teacher / mentor	47	30.7%
Online tutorials	39	25.5%
Usually cannot get help	12	7.8%

— WHERE RESPONDENTS LOOK FOR HELP

In critical situations, 4 of 10 respondents prefer to look for the help of their friends/family, 3 of 10 respondents ask a youth worker/teacher/mentor for assistance, and 2 of 10 respondents discuss an issue in online tutorials. However, 1 of 10 respondents **usually can't get help**. This is crucial for taking into consideration when planning support for young migrants.

“

"Mantenerlo todo organizado, ver qué archivos ya no son necesarios."

— 06.5 · CITY DIFFERENCES

City-level differences.

Learning format preferences vary by city, a reminder that **"one-size-fits-all" doesn't work**. Local routines, transport and service access shape what young migrants will realistically engage with.

RESPONDENTS' PREFERRED LEARNING FORMAT IN THE CITIES OF THE PARTNER COUNTRIES

LOCATION	YM (N)	PREFERRED LEARNING FORMAT
Fundão	13	Online sessions
Córdoba	19	In-person workshops
Riga	18	Mixed learning
	8	Peer learning

— LOCAL CONTEXT

These results show that learning format should fit local routines, including transport and service access.

07

Youth Workers and IWMRs.

*Responses from youth workers and professionals
from institutions working with migrants and
refugees across the three partner countries.*

 07.1 · YW ACCESS

Digital access in services.

Many services already offer some practical support for access. **About two-thirds** of the respondents said their organisations provide devices that are adequate for young people to take part in activities. Therefore, many youth workers' teams already have digital devices to build on.

ACCESS IN SERVICES

68.6%

Organisation provides adequate devices

54.3%

Young people do not have Pro tools

45.7%

Staff have Pro tools

At the same time, **about one-third** said their organisation does not have this support. Even when an organisation has devices, they may be limited in number, shared between groups, or available only at certain times. The respondents also pointed out a gap with paid tools. When asked about "Pro" versions (paid tools such as design, translation or learning platforms), 6 of 10 young people **do not have access**. Staff access is better as about 5 of the 10 respondents have access to paid tools. However, more than one third of the respondents' access to paid tools is not guaranteed. For daily youth work, paid subscriptions to work well in digital non-formal education is crucial.

 PRACTICE BETWEEN SESSIONS

If young people can only practise during the workshop (and not between sessions), progress will often be slower, not because they don't care, but because they can't access the same tools at home. If activities rely on paid platforms, some young people will be left out.

— 07.2 · CAPACITY

Capacity and engagement.

Most professionals describe their own working conditions as digitally stable. 8 of 10 respondents **rate their internet connection as good**. That suggests the majority can run online tasks, meetings, and coordination without constant connection problems. Most of the respondents use digital tools as a normal part of work. About two-thirds of the respondents **use digital tools every day**. Therefore, youth workers are digitally competent. However, the challenge is that young people's access and confidence vary a lot. In these conditions, youth workers spend their time on troubleshooting, translation, and encouragement instead of educating and serving youth. In accordance with the inquiry's results, 8 of 10 of the respondents feel confident about their digital skills.

YOUNG MIGRANTS' ENGAGEMENT WITH DIGITAL ACTIVITIES

— ENGAGEMENT AND CONDITIONS

The results indicate that youth workers recognise that engagement often depends on whether young people have the tools, time, language support, and confidence, and whether the activity aligns well to their real lives. Engagement is not a fixed "type of person" thing. It changes based on the conditions around the young person. When tasks feel immediately useful (job applications, services, communication), engagement often improves.

07.3 · CONSTRAINTS

Constraints and barriers.

A half of the respondents highlighted that the common issue refers to **young people's irregular access to devices/internet**. 4 of 10 respondents stresses **limited resources**, such as staff time, equipment, or budgets, in services. Frequent **language and translation barriers** were pointed by each 4th of 10 respondents. **Low motivation/engagement**, often linked to the barriers above, was noted by one third of the respondents.

RESPONDENTS' CONSTRAINTS AND BARRIERS IN PROVIDING SERVICES TO YOUNG MIGRANTS

— IMPACT ON MOTIVATION

These results show that when a young person tries to fill a form on a phone in a language they don't fully control, motivation can drop quickly, not because they don't want to learn, but because it's exhausting and frustrating.

— IMPACT FOR SERVICE DESIGN

Services need time for support, not only "teaching time". Language support and visual materials are not "extra"; they are part of what makes learning possible.

07.4 · PRIORITIES

Priorities and tools.

The inquiry's results show that 8 of 10 respondents wish support young people with **online public and social services**, creating **CVs and job profiles online**, and running **online sessions / online meetings** confidently. The analysed data reveals that the respondents have a clear picture about the kinds of support they want to provide. Its' focus is on everyday tasks young people face in integration, learning and work. Three quarters of the respondents consider important to teach **basic computer and internet skills**, to support intercultural digital activities, and to ensure safe, respectful online communication.

SKILLS AND COMPETENCIES THE RESPONDENTS WISH TO STRENGTHEN

DIGITAL TOOLS USED BY THE RESPONDENTS

TOOLS ALREADY USED IN SERVICES	N	%
Messaging & video	58	82.9%
Collaboration / project tools	47	67.1%
AI tools	43	61.4%
Content creation / design	38	54.3%

IMPACT ON TRAINING AND RESOURCES

8 of 10 respondents use messaging & video tools. Collaboration/project tools and AI tools are utilised by 6 of 10 respondents. Design/content tools are in use by more than a half of the respondents. This help finding that support is not only "more tools", it also includes **simple guidance and session materials** that help teams use the tools, they already rely on, in a safe and inclusive way.

08

Recommendations.

For youth workers and IWMRs who want to turn these findings into everyday action.

08.A · INCLUSION

Inclusion, trust and participation.

Together with digital skills, digital learning for many young migrants is also about **confidence, safety, and feeling that they belong in the space**. The inquiry shows that two-thirds of young migrants are highly interested in learning. However, young migrants need support in overcoming several barriers: nearly half do not have a laptop, and more than half have been blocked from completing online tasks because of access or technical issues. Therefore, their participation is often shaped by **conditions**, not their motivation.

A SIMPLE RULE THAT HELPS

When a young person struggles, assume it's **access, language, or stress** before assuming it's "lack of interest".

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR INCLUSIVE DIGITAL NFE

- 01 Plan for phone-first participation**
Design materials that work well on a phone. Offer access to a computer when needed.
 - 02 Build "help time" into every session**
Logins, email setup, saving files, attaching documents, these aren't side tasks. They're learning moments.
 - 03 Use the buddy system**
Pair work reduces shame around asking for help. It also turns peer-to-peer support into a normal part of learning.
 - 04 Make joining easy, make returning easier**
Clear time/place, friendly reminders, simple registration. Heavy admin loses people.
-

08.B · DESIGN

Designing digital learning.

The inquiry results reveal that 6 of 10 respondents' learning need is **job search and CV tools**. 5 of 10 respondents wish to increase their **basic computer and internet skills**. 4 of 10 respondents want to enhance their knowledge about AI tools and creative tools. This helps finding that both "practical" and "creative" learning, as long as it's done safely, should be delivered.

LEARNING PRIORITIES. YM VS YW

DIGITAL NON-FORMAL EDUCATION TOPICS	YOUNG MIGRANTS	YOUTH WORKERS
Job search and CV tools	57.5%	81.4%
Online public/social services	51.0%	82.9%

These data point that young migrants want learning that helps with real needs, especially employability and daily online tasks. This finding is confirmed by the youth workers who responded to the survey questionnaire as 8 of 10 respondents from the youth workers' sample consider that **online public/social services** and **CV/job profiles** are core priorities in non-formal education. The results of both survey questionnaires provide evidence that both youth services and young people consider similar topics to be included in non-formal education.

DIGITAL SAFETY AND PRIVACY

Digital safety and privacy should be a normal part of learning. Privacy is one of the areas where only one third respondents, who are young migrants, reported lower confidence (35.7%). Don't treat it as an extra topic. Embed privacy habits throughout multiple sessions, using simple language and real examples, not legal jargon or fear-based messages.

SESSION DESIGN PRINCIPLES

- 01 Lead with useful tasks**
 Start with CVs, job search, online services. Teach basics through those tasks (files, email, forms).
- 02 Don't assume the starting level**
 Even daily internet users may not feel confident with the skills needed for school, work and services.
- 03 Mix in-person and online**
 In-person workshops build trust. Mixed formats give flexibility. Fully online is rarely the answer.

08.C · DO & AVOID

Do and avoid.

Practical do's and don'ts for setting up young migrants' cooperation with youth service organisations.

✓ DO

Helps in real settings

- Start with useful tasks like CV, job search, and online services.
- Plan for phone use and limited access.
- Build "help time" into the session (logins, email, saving files).
- Teach privacy as simple habits.
- Offer in-person or mixed formats when possible.
- Make it easy to join and easy to return (clear time/place; friendly reminders).

✗ AVOID

Often makes people drop out

- Starting with long theory sessions or complex tool lists.
- Assuming everyone has a laptop and stable Wi-Fi.
- Rushing through content without time for support.
- Using fear-based messages or legal language that confuses people.
- Online-only learning as the default.
- Heavy registration steps and unclear follow-up.

— TRAUMA-AWARE AND CULTURALLY RESPECTFUL FACILITATION

Some young people may be under stress, and digital tasks can trigger worry (fear of making mistakes, fear of sharing the wrong information, fear of being judged). When confidence is low, reduce pressure and increase clarity. Allow multiple attempts. Avoid public correction. Use familiar visual cues.

— A KEY POINT

A key point is that when a young person says "I don't know where to learn", that is a signal to make learning offers **more visible, attractive, and easier to access**.

— 08.C · YOUTH SERVICES

Youth services for NFE.

More than one third of young migrants said they **don't know where to learn** and expressed their need in **mentor support**. This is not just a training issue; it's a "how services connect" issue.

Digital inclusion usually improves faster when youth work does not act alone. It works best when there is **cooperation with youth service organizations**: youth centres, municipalities, integration teams, schools and community organisations.

WHERE THE FRICTION IS

ISSUE	YM RESPONDENTS (N)	%
Don't know where to learn	58	37.9%
Need mentor support	50	32.7%

CHECKLIST OF SUPPORT MEASURES BY YOUTH SERVICES

Youth services do not have to take every item into consideration, but the more barriers youth service can reduce, the easier learning becomes.

-
Provide stable devices and connectivity
 Especially during sessions. Lend laptops when possible.

-
Offer mentor / buddy support
 Both inside and outside sessions. Follow-up matters.

-
Make information visible
 Where to learn, when, how to join. Posters, social media, partner networks.

-
Use simple language
 Bilingual glossary, visual materials, repeated instructions.

-
Coordinate across organisations
 Schools, IWMRs, libraries, employment offices. Share referrals.

-
Low-literacy adaptations
 Visual icons, oral instructions, allow peer or facilitator to write.

09

Inquiry impact on the project.

From insight to action, how the inquiry's findings reshape YouthConnect's training, tools and workshop design.

09.1 · KEY CONTRIBUTIONS

Key contributions of the inquiry report.

This inquiry report was prepared to help the YouthConnect partners and other organisations across Europe working in this field make training **practical decisions** that fit the real lives of young migrants and the real working conditions of youth workers and integration services by including the three key points: about what to train, what to build, and how to run activities. The inquiry report explains **what we learned** and **what YouthConnect training should be**.

SIX KEY INQUIRY FINDINGS → TRAINING IMPLICATIONS

- 01 Motivation is there but conditions decide if learning is possible**
Workshops and tools must work well for people using phones, and services must offer chances to use a computer when needed.

- 02 The strongest learning request is about work and opportunities**
Employability-related digital learning will be a core focus across the project.

- 03 Basic skills still matter, even for young people who are online daily**
The project must include beginner-friendly materials and step-by-step practice sessions, without assuming starting levels.

- 04 Digital safety has to be practical and normal**
Safety and privacy will be included throughout activities, using simple language and real examples (not legal language or fear-based messages).

- 05 Online services are part of inclusion**
Workshops and training will include practical skills for online forms, appointments, and service platforms, because this is part of daily integration reality.

- 06 Many young people need support, not just resources**
Activities need built-in support moments (help time, buddying, and clear follow-up), not only content delivery.

09.2 · TRAINING PROPOSAL

YouthConnect training proposal.

For the improvement of the situation with young migrants' inclusion, the YouthConnect project proposal for training young migrants is structured around three elements.

A. TRAINING COURSE FOR YOUTH WORKERS

The training for youth workers and professionals focuses on the areas, that both groups agree, are urgent:

- Helping young people with CVs, job profiles and job search
- Teaching basic computer and internet skills in a calm, inclusive way
- Supporting young people with online services
- Building safe online habits and respectful communication
- Running sessions that work when access is uneven

The training will be strongly about **how to run sessions**, how to support a mixed group, and how to keep learning safe and respectful.

B. DIGITAL NFE TOOLS / OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

The inquiry shaped what the project will build into its tools and materials:

- Materials that are easy to use on a phone
- Step-by-step guides that support basic digital tasks, CV building and online forms
- Simple privacy and safety guides using everyday language
- Templates and checklists that reduce staff workload

C. DELIVERY OF DIGITAL WORKSHOPS + DIGITAL ART STORYTELLING WORKSHOPS

Young migrants prefer learning with human support. In-person workshops and mixed learning are prioritized compared to fully online. In-person sessions, with optional online support where it fits local reality are selected for workshops, including:

- time for help with logins, saving files, and forms
- small group work where asking for help is normal
- clear rules for privacy and consent when creating or sharing content

09.3 · INSIGHT TO ACTION

From insight to action.

How the inquiry findings translate into concrete project decisions.

WHAT THE INQUIRY SHOWED	WHAT IT MEANS IN PRACTICE	WHAT YOUTHCONNECT WILL DO	WHO LEADS	WHEN
Many young migrants are interested but are blocked by access/tech issues	Interest is real; access decides participation	Build phone-friendly materials + offer computer time in sessions	Local youth services	During workshops
Almost half of young migrants do not own a laptop	Some tasks are hard outside sessions	Provide in-session device access and low-data resources	Municipal / partner spaces	During workshops
Top young migrants learning need: job search & CV tools	Employability content motivates learning	Make CV / job profile a main workshop topic	Training + local teams	Early workshops
Basic skills are also a top young migrants need and youth workers priority	Don't assume starting level	Include beginner-friendly steps and repetition	Trainers + facilitators	All phases
Privacy is a weaker skill area	Safety must be normal and practical	Embed privacy habits in multiple sessions	Facilitators	All phases
Youth workers top priority: online public/social services	Inclusion includes service navigation	Add practice with online forms / appointments	Local teams	Mid workshops
Many young migrants need mentor support and some can't get help	Support must be built-in	Add "help time" + buddy support + follow-up	Local teams	All phases

EXPLOITATION OF YOUTHCONNECT INQUIRY RESULTS

Even outside the project, the inquiry points to a simple approach that many youth services, including non-formal education, can use: **start with what young people find useful (CVs, services, communication); teach basics through those tasks (files, email, forms); plan for uneven access (phones, shared devices, limited data); make privacy and respect part of everyday learning; built-in help, because many young people need support to keep going.**

10 · CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions.

This YouthConnect Inquiry reveals the daily practice, well known to many youth workers and integration teams, that digital inclusion is about both learning tools and having the right conditions to learn, having someone to help and feeling connected to real life.

The inquiry shows that many young people are online every day and wish to join digital non-formal education.

The inquiry indicates that access problems create critical barriers for participation of even motivated young people. Nearly half do not have an own laptop or computer, and more than half have technical or access issues. Youth services should be able to provide stable devices, time, and support.

Job search and CV tools as well as basic computer and internet skills are the topics of high interest of young migrants. The inquiry results confirm that the youth workers consider the same topics as crucial for young migrants.

Youth workers include online public and social services in training for young migrants.

The inquiry highlights that young migrants are interested to learn about online safety and privacy. Youth workers have a similar selection, too. Online safety and privacy should be integrated into youth work and training and become an everyday habit of young migrants.

Young migrants expressed the need in mentor support. Young migrants cannot solve their issues in host countries without mentor guidance.

In-person workshops are highly preferred by young migrants. Youth centres, municipal spaces, and community organisations should ensure learning places where learning can occur.

These results show that **digital inclusion promotes social and economic inclusion as well**. Therefore, training for young migrants should include non-formal education tools that work on phones and computers, digital devices, preparation of CVs/jobs, use of online services, their safety and privacy.

11 · CONTACTS

Contacts.

For more information about the YouthConnect project, the inquiry, or any of the resources mentioned in this report, contact the consortium partners.

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YOUTHCONNECT PLATFORM

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